

Morphological Variations of Liver- A Cadaveric Study in Telangana Region

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Abstract

Background: The study of liver variations in cadavers is crucial for enhancing anatomical knowledge, as the liver exhibits significant variability in its lobes and blood supply. Understanding these variations is vital for surgical planning and diagnostic procedures. Cadaveric studies provide direct insights into anatomical differences, aiding clinicians in managing liver-related conditions and reducing intraoperative complications.

Methods: This observational study was conducted on 50 formalin-fixed human livers that were removed from cadavers during routine dissection for medical undergraduates and were preserved in 10% formalin. Livers with a normal configuration were included and damaged and deformed livers were excluded from the study. The livers were examined on a flat, sterile surface under adequate lighting. Each lobe of the liver was observed in detail, focusing on the size, shape, and anatomical variations. The lobes were classified according to the Netter classification system.

Results: Out of the total 50 livers studied in this study 29 (58%) specimens showed variations. Accessory fissures on the right lobe were found in 26.7% of the cases. Morphological variations based on Netter's classification, found approximately 42% of the livers examined were classified as normal (Type I). Types II (very small left lobe, deep coastal impression) and VI- Very deep renal impression and corset constriction were found in 8%, and IV (transverse saddle liver, relatively large left lobe) in 12% were the most common variations after the normal type. No type III livers were found in this study.

Conclusion: The current study highlights the frequent occurrence of morphological variations on the surface of the liver. These variations are important in the case of laparoscopic removal/thermal ablation of the liver mass; therefore, knowledge of these variations is important for surgeons and gastroenterologists in planning and performing surgical procedures for radiologists to prevent possible misdiagnosis and for anatomists to find new variants.

Keywords: Liver, Morphological Variations, Surgical Procedures, Netter's Classification.

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Introduction

The liver is the largest abdominal organ located in the right hypochondrium, epigastric, and left hypochondrium. The liver has four lobes: right, left, caudate, and quadrate [1]. The right and left lobes are anteriorly separated by the attachment of the falciform ligament, posteriorly by the fissure of the ligamentum venosum, and inferiorly by the fissure of the ligamentum teres on the left side. The caudate and quadrate lobes are bounded by the groove of the IVC and gallbladder fossa [1]. Variations in morphology can be either congenital or acquired. Congenital abnormalities of the liver include agenesis, atrophy or hypoplasia of the lobes, accessory lobes, and accessory fissures. The Accessory lobes are present in 10% of the Indian population [2]. They might be mistaken for a lymph node because of its small size and removal

during surgery [2]. Accessory Fissures are a potential source of diagnostic errors during imaging. It may be mistaken for a liver cyst, hematoma, or abscess if there is a collection of fluid in these fissures. Metastatic tumor cells lodging into these spaces may mimic focal lesions [2]. Acquired variations in the liver could be due to the pressure exerted by the diaphragm, peritoneal ligaments, and other organs in relation to the liver, which develops during the lifetime of a person [2]. Hepatic anomalies may be due to excessive growth during embryonic life or defective development of the liver. The latter leads to the formation of A/L and A/F on the hepatic surface [3]. Most A/F disappears during liver reformation in the postnatal period, but some can persist for life [4]. The localization of major fissures contributes to the

interpretation of lobar anatomy and localization of lesions [5]. Currently, knowledge of this type of variation is important for surgeons and gastroenterologists in planning and performing surgical procedures, for radiologists to prevent possible misdiagnosis and unnecessary surgical complications, and for anatomists to identify new variations [5]. The present study aimed to evaluate gross anatomical variations of the liver and their clinical implications

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted on 50 formalin-fixed human livers from embalmed cadavers in the Department of Anatomy, Osmania Medical College, Hyderabad, Telangana, after obtaining prior approval from the institutional ethical committee. Liver specimens were removed from cadavers during routine dissection for medical undergraduates and were preserved in 10% formalin. Livers with a normal configuration were included and damaged and deformed livers were excluded from the study. The livers were examined on a flat, sterile surface under adequate lighting. Each lobe of the liver was observed in detail, focusing on the size, shape, and anatomical variations. The lobes were classified according to the Netter classification system, which includes the following divisions:

- Right Lobe.
- Left Lobe.
- Caudate Lobe.

Figure 1: AF on right lobe

Figure 2: Deep Renal impression

- Quadrate Lobe.

High-resolution photographs were obtained to document the morphology and variations of each liver specimen. Photographs were captured from multiple angles to ensure comprehensive documentation of all observable features. A scale was included in each photograph for reference size. All observations and classifications were independently verified by two Experienced anatomists to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Data Recording and Analysis: Detailed notes were taken regarding the morphological characteristics of each liver and uploaded to MS Excel Spreadsheet. Data were recorded in a structured format with no deviations from the typical Netter classification. Statistical analysis was conducted to determine the frequency of the observed variations among the specimens.

Results

The present study was conducted on 50 livers, of which 21(42%) were normal without any accessory fissures/lobes. The remaining 29 (58%) specimens showed variations, such as accessory fissures, deep renal impressions, pons hepatitis, and absence/incomplete fissures for LT.

Right Lobe: In the present study, 24 (48%) specimens showed accessory fissures of varying lengths and depth [Fig-1]. Deep renal impression was observed in four (8%) livers [Fig -2]. In four (8%) liver specimens, prominent vertical grooves were observed due to compression of the liver by the diaphragm [Fig -3].

Figure 3: Diaphragmatic grooves

Figure 4: AF on left lobe

Left Lobe: Accessory fissures were observed in 6 (12%) livers over various areas of the left lobe [Fig -4] Small left lobe was identified in 4(8%) liver specimens [Fig-5], and an elongated left lobe was seen in 8(16%) livers [Fig -6]

Figure 5: Small left lobe

Figure 6: Elongated left lobe

Caudate Lobe: Out of 29 liver specimens, 14(28%) livers showed Accessory fissures [Fig-7], and the thin caudate lobe was observed in 6(12%) livers [Fig -8].

Figure 7: AF on caudate lobe

Figure 8: Thin caudate lobe

Quadrangle Lobe: Accessory fissures were observed in 11 (22%) livers [Fig -9] and a thin quadrangle lobe was observed in 6(12%).

Figure 9: AF on quadrate lobe

Figure 10: Pons hepatitis

Pons hepatitis extending from the quadrate lobe to the left lobe was observed in 2(4%) livers [Fig-10]. Absence of fissure for ligament teres was seen in 6(12%) livers [Fig-11]

Figure 11: Absence of fissure for ligament teres

Table 1 presents the frequency of various morphological variations observed in the liver. Approximately 42% of the livers examined were considered normal, exhibiting no morphological variations. The most common variation was the

presence of accessory fissures, with the right lobe being the most frequent location. Deep renal impressions, diaphragmatic grooves, pons hepatitis, and absence of the fissure for the left lobe were observed with lower frequencies.

Table 1: Showing morphological variations of liver in the present study

Type of variation	No of Specimens
Normal Liver	21(42%)
Accessory fissures on the right lobe	24 (26.7%)
Accessory fissures on the left lobe	6 (28.9%)
Accessory fissures on caudate lobe	14 (15.6%)
Accessory fissures on the quadrate lobe	11 (12.2%)
Deep renal impressions	4 (4.4%)
Diaphragmatic grooves	5 (5.6%)
Pons hepatitis	2 (2.2%)
Absence of fissure for LT	6 (6.7%)

Note: some of the livers examined had more than one abnormality present simultaneously

Table 2 categorizes liver morphological variations based on Netter's classification. Approximately 42% of the livers examined were classified as normal (Type I). Types II (very small left lobe, deep coastal impression) and IV (transverse saddle liver, relatively large left lobe) were the most common variations after the normal type. Types III (complete atrophy of left lobe) and V (tongue-like

process of right lobe) were not observed in the study population.

Table 2: Showing morphological variations of the liver according to Netter's classification

Type of Variation	No of Specimens
I-Normal	21 (42%)
II- Very small left lobe, deep coastal impression	4 (8%)
III- Complete atrophy of left lobe	0(0.0)
IV- Transverse saddle liver, relatively large left lobe	6 (12%)
V- Tongue-like process of the right lobe	0(0.0)
VI- Very deep renal impression & corset constriction	4 (8%)
VII- Diaphragmatic grooves	2(10%)

Discussion

Knowledge of anatomical variations in the liver is important for clinicians, surgeons, and radiologists to minimize complications during procedures, hepatic interventions, and other surgical procedures [3]. Liver development starts early in the 3rd -4th week of intrauterine life. The most Common gross variations are irregularities in form compared to accessory lobes [6]. Variations in the liver can be congenital or acquired. Congenital anomalies of the

liver occur due to defects or excessive development [6]. Defective development of the left lobe can lead to gastric volvulus, while defective development of the right lobe may remain latent or progress to portal HTN. Excessive development of the liver results in the formation of accessory lobes, which may carry the risk of torsion [6]. Variations in the morphology of the liver include accessory fissures, linguliform lobes, small left lobes, deep renal impressions, and corset-type constriction [6].

Table 3: Showing comparison of accessory fissures of the liver by various studies

Author & year	Sample size	Rt lobe	Lt lobe	Caudate lobe	Quadrante lobe
Haobam et al. 2018 [2]	70	36 (51%)	8 (11%)	19 (27%)	23 (33%)
Kumar Sambhav et al. 2023 [4]	40	29 (73%)	12 (30%)	23 (58%)	7 (18%)
Sarita et al. 2015 [7]	50	8 (16%)	1 (2%)	3 (6%)	5 (10%)
Sangeeta et al. 2023 [8]	50	10 (20%)	-	4 (8%)	3 (6%)
Present study 2024	50	24 (48%)	6 (12%)	14 (28%)	15 (30%)

Table 4 presents data from three different studies on liver morphological variations, specifically focusing on the presence of Pons Hepatitis and the absence of fissures in the left lobe. The prevalence of Pons Hepatitis ranges from 1.2% to 8%, with a

general trend towards higher incidence in recent studies. The absence of fissures in the left lobe showed a wider range (0% to 11%), with the highest incidence reported in the present study.

Table 4: Showing comparison of variations of liver by various studies

Author & year	Sample size	Pons Hepatitis	Absence of fissure for LT
Heena et al 2017 [5]	80	1 (1.2%)	9 (11%)
Sarita et al 2015 [7]	50	2 (4%)	0 (0.0%)
Dhanalaxmi et al 2019 [9]	50	4 (8%)	1 (2%)
Present study 2024	50	2 (4%)	5 (10%)

Table 5: Showing comparison of variations of the liver by various studies according to Netter's classification.

Author & year	Sample size	Type-I	Type - II	Type-IV	Type-VI	Type-VII
K Sambhav et al. 2023 [4]	40	22(50%)	4 (10%)	7(18%)	3 (8%)	3 (8%)
Heena et al. 2017 [5]	80	14 (18%)	14(18%)	10 (13%)	1 (1.3%)	6 (8%)
Sangeeta et al. 2023 [8]	50	28 (56%)	4 (8%)	4 (8%)	2 (4%)	10 (20%)
Dhanalaxmi et al 2019 [9]	50	04 (8%)	-	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	3 (6%)
Present study 2024	50	21(42%)	4 (8%)	8 (16%)	4 (8%)	2 (8%)

A comparative analysis of liver morphological variations based on Netter's classification across

four different studies is presented in Table 5. The prevalence of different liver types varied

significantly across studies. Type I (normal liver) and Type II (very small left lobe, deep coastal impression) showed the highest frequency in most studies. The present study reported a higher prevalence of Type I (normal liver) compared with other studies. A study by Heena et al. showed a higher prevalence of Type II and IV variations.

The absence of Type III (complete atrophy of the left lobe) and Type V (tongue-like process of the right lobe) in multiple studies indicates a relatively low prevalence of these variations, highlighting the heterogeneity in the prevalence of liver morphological variations across different populations. Factors such as geographic location, ethnic background, and diagnostic methodologies may contribute to these differences. The data from this study emphasize the need for larger multicentre studies to establish more reliable estimates of liver variation frequencies.

Limitations: The comparative analysis underscores the importance of considering liver anatomical variations in clinical practice and research. Further studies with standardized methodologies and larger sample sizes are necessary to refine our understanding of the global distribution of liver morphological variations.

Conclusion

The current study highlights the frequent occurrence of morphological variations on the surface of the liver. These variations are important in the case of laparoscopic removal/thermal ablation of the liver mass; therefore, knowledge of these variations is important for surgeons and gastroenterologists in planning and performing surgical procedures for radiologists to prevent possible misdiagnosis and for anatomists to find new variants.

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